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Sustainable Beekeeping, from the south of the world

ABSTRACT BOOK

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OP-114

The *Vespa orientalis* Linnaeus 1771 (Hymenoptera: Vespidae) issue in Chile: The urgency of taking control measures through collaboration between beekeepers, specialists, and the government

José Contreras

Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Valparaíso, Valparaíso, Chile

The *Vespa orientalis* Linnaeus 1771 (Hymenoptera: Vespidae), also known as the Asian hornet, is a eusocial wasp native to the Northern Hemisphere and mainly distributed in Eurasia and North Africa. It is a well-known species in countries such as Malta, Spain, Italy, and Israel, where it causes significant losses to beekeeping and fruit cultivation, and can cause complex symptoms, including renal failure and even death, particularly in children.

In May 2019, the species was first recorded in Santiago, Chile, and the first scientific record was published in 2020, including specimens collected outside a nest in the San Bernardo commune of the Metropolitan Region of Santiago. To date, the species has been recorded in multiple communes in the Metropolitan Region, with at least two nests collected, cases of human stings reported, and recent sightings in at least three locations in the O'Higgins region.

Given the lack of government measures for monitoring and managing this species in Chile, we aim to provide an update on its distribution in Chile and provide guidelines for joint actions among specialists, beekeepers, and government institutions (SAG, INIA, and MINSAL). This will be based on scientific evidence and the experiences of international specialists and beekeepers.

Our study includes new distribution records, physical nest collections, conversations with beekeepers, and collaboration with international specialists who have experience in controlling this species. The evidence collected supports the urgency of implementing control measures and the need for collaborative actions among stakeholders to minimize the negative impact of this invasive species on the environment, beekeeping, and public health.

In summary, our study highlights the urgent need for measures to control the spread of *Vespa orientalis* in Chile and the importance of collaboration among specialists, beekeepers, and government institutions to address this issue.

OP-115

Beekeeping in Cuba: Selection, Resistance, and Diseases

Adolfo Pérez Piñeiro¹, Anais Rodríguez¹, Carlos Ariel Yadró¹, Alejandro Pérez Morfi¹, Carlos Enrique Rodríguez Rosell¹, Ivanna H Tomasco², Karina Antúnez³, Belén Branchiccela⁴, Ciro Invernizzi⁵, Isobel Grindrod⁶, Georgiana Webb⁶, Stephen Martin⁶

¹Centro de Investigaciones Apícolas, La Habana, Cuba

²Departamento de Ecología y Evolución, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de la República, Montevideo, Uruguay

³Laboratorio de Microbiología y Salud de las Abejas, Departamento de Microbiología, Instituto de Investigaciones Biológicas Clemente Estable, Montevideo, Uruguay

⁴Sección Apicultura, Instituto Nacional de Investigación Agropecuaria, Colonia, Uruguay

⁵Sección Etología, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de la República, Montevideo, Uruguay

⁶University of Salford, Manchester M5 4WT, UK

Since the beginning of the 80s of the 20th century, Cuba has worked on the selection of bees with the aim of achieving greater honey productivity and resistance to infectious diseases and *Varroa*. However, it wasn't until 2017 that the genetic composition of the Cuban honey bee population was evaluated, and a diagnosis of its main diseases was made using molecular biology tools. These investigations demonstrated that the populations of *Apis mellifera* in Cuba have a European origin (80% similarity with mitochondrial haplotypes), but with differences due to genetic isolation. In addition to the Korean haplotype of *Varroa destructor*, we also detected the presence of *Nosema ceranae*, Acute bee paralysis virus (ABPV), Deformed wing virus (DWW) and Sacbrood bee virus (SBV) in the Cuban colonies. Nevertheless, there have been no reports of hive deaths due to these bee diseases circulating in the country. Said genetic isolation combined with an acaricide-free beekeeping have possibly influenced the fixation and expression of *Varroa*-resistance genes, leading to the high rates of recapping of *Varroa*-infested worker cells (72 %), high removal of mites (81 %) and corresponding low mite fertility ($r = 0.77$), that we also found in Cuban colonies.

